

Investigation of Fuel Cell Behavior with Different Catalyst Loadings at Varying Humidities and Temperatures

Yurii V. Yakovlev^z, Yevheniia V. Lobko, Miquel Gamón Rodríguez, Alina Madalina Darabut, Lucinda Blanco Redondo, Iva Matolínová

Charles University, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Department of Surface and Plasma Science, V Holešovičkách 2, 18000 Prague 8, Czech Republic

^z yurii.yakovlev@matfyz.cuni.cz

Abstract

Proton exchange membrane fuel cells, which are suitable for operation at low humidities, are important for the practical application of fuel cell-based systems. In this work, we study the performance and durability of Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) fuel cells with varying Pt loadings (ranging from 0.2 to 1 mg cm⁻²) and ionomer carbon ratios (0.6 and 0.8) in cathode catalyst layers under different operating humidities and temperatures. It was found that performance is affected by relative humidity, reaching a maximum at 75%RH for loading <0.4 mg_{Pt} cm⁻² and at 50%RH for loading > 0.8 mg_{Pt} cm⁻². An increase in the I/C ratio to 0.8 was found to impair fuel cell performance at high humidity levels while enhancing performance and durability under low humidity operation.

1. Introduction

Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) fuel cells have emerged as a promising alternative to traditional power sources due to their high energy conversion efficiency, reduced emissions, and potential for clean energy generation [1]. However, one of the challenges associated with PEM fuel cells is their sensitivity to operating conditions, particularly at low humidity. In such an environment, especially at elevated temperatures, rapid dehydration of the ionomer phase and membrane dramatically reduces proton conductivity and, as a result, the overall performance [2,3]. In a dry environment, low proton conductivity in the catalyst layer renders the majority of catalyst particles inactive [4]. In addition, membranes demonstrate high ohmic overpotential and low fuel cell performance at high current densities. More-

25 over, the durability of PEM fuel cells is significantly affected at low humidity levels [5].
26 External humidifiers are required to control the humidity levels and fuel performance [6]. However, the addition of
27 humidifiers increases the cost and weight of the system and may be appropriate for stationary or high-power mobile
28 systems. In contrast, medium-power solutions such as portable power generators or unmanned aerial vehicles often
29 use open-cathode or air-breathing designs [7,8]. These designs face challenges in achieving proper water management
30 and often exhibit poor performance due to dehydration.

31 Improving the water retention properties of the membrane [9], gas diffusion [10-12], microporous [13,14], and cata-
32 lyst layer [13,15–17], among others, can improve fuel cell performance at low humidity. Alternatively, adjusting the
33 catalyst layer loading and thickness may also impact the performance. For example, increasing Pt loading improves
34 reaction kinetics, as observed in a study on air-breathing microbial fuel cells, where increasing Pt loading from 0.2 to
35 2 mg cm⁻² boosted fuel cell performance [18]. However, high loadings and thicker catalyst layers can impede mass
36 transport, potentially affecting performance, as noted in [19]. Therefore, determining the optimal catalyst loading is
37 necessary to achieve the best fuel cell performance [20]. While much of the recent research focus has been on achiev-
38 ing ultra-low Pt loadings (≤ 0.1 mgPt cm⁻²) [21-23], the durability and stable performance required for commercial
39 and heavy-duty applications still rely on more moderate loadings ≥ 0.2 mgPt cm⁻² [24], due to their higher reliability
40 [25, 26]. The fundamental interactions between water management, ionomer content, and catalyst loading in these
41 practically relevant systems are not fully understood. Our study addresses this specific knowledge gap.

42 Thus, the objective of this study is to systematically investigate and map the interactions between these key param-
43 eters. By varying the cathode catalyst loading (from 0.2 to 1.0 mg_{Pt} cm⁻²), the ionomer-to-carbon (I/C) ratio, the operat-
44 ing humidity and temperature, we aim to elucidate the complex trade-offs between reaction kinetics, mass transport,
45 and water management. The goal is to establish clear design principles that connect catalyst layer composition to op-
46 timal performance and durability, providing a crucial guide for the development of reliable fuel cell systems.

47 **2. Experimental**

48 2.1. Catalyst ink preparation.

49 For catalyst ink preparation, 250 mg of catalyst powder (Pt40% @Vulcan) was prewetted with 2 ml of acetone in the
50 glass vial to prevent a catalytic burning of isopropanol vapours. Then, 1.8 ml of the ionomer dispersion (D-521, 5%

51 PFSA dispersion) was poured in, followed by dilution in the mixture of acetone (8 ml) and isopropanol (10 ml). The
52 prepared mixture was homogenised using a horn-type ultrasonicator (HD-3100, Bandeling SonoPulse) for 20 min
53 with a 5 s on/off working cycle. To prevent the dispersion overheating the vial was cooled with an ice bath. The cata-
54 lyst ink composition was optimized for the preparation of catalyst layers with an ionomer-to-carbon (I/C) ratio of 0.6.
55 Formulation of the catalyst ink with I/C = 0.8 differed in the increased amount of ionomer dispersion, 2.4 ml, with the
56 rest of the routine same.

57 2.2 CCM preparation

58 Catalyst-coated membranes were prepared by using ultrasonic spraying (ExactaCoat, Sono-Tek) of the catalyst ink
59 onto the cation exchange membrane (Fumapem FS-715-RFS, 15 μm of thickness). Fast solvent evaporation from the
60 catalyst layer was guaranteed by securing the membrane on the preheated plate to 65 °C. The spraying procedure was
61 optimised to increase the catalyst loading by 0.05 $\text{mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$ every cycle. Catalyst loading for the cathode catalyst lay-
62 er (CCL) had values of 0.2, 0.4, 0.8, and 1.0 $\text{mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$. Anode catalyst layer loading was the same for all samples and
63 equal to 0.3 $\text{mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$. The desired loading was achieved by controlling the number of spraying cycles. A constant
64 geometric area of 4 cm^2 was ensured by using a cover mask with a precut 2x2 cm^2 window. Prepared catalyst-coated
65 membranes (CCMs) were stored in the box, and no additional pretreatment was used before measurements.

66 2.3 Fuel cell measurements.

67 The prepared CCMs were sandwiched between two pieces of gas diffusion layer (GDL) with a micro-porous layer
68 (H24C5, Freudenberg) with an area of 4 cm^2 each. This membrane electrode assembly (MEA) was sealed in the
69 graphite cell with a single serpentine flow field. The testing equipment allows constant temperature and humidity op-
70 eration. Cell temperature was set at 40, 50, 60, and 70 °C; the relative humidity of gases was controlled by setting the
71 proper dew point of the bubbler humidifier and balanced at 100, 75, 50, and 25%. Experiments in a totally dry envi-
72 ronment were conducted using a humidifier bypass valve. Conditioning of the fuel cell at each set of temperature and
73 humidity is performed at a constant gas flow of 50 sccm for 6 hours.

74 Measurements of fuel cell polarization curves were done after the break-in process described in [19]. Polarisation
75 curves were measured in the galvanostatic mode with 5 mA cm^{-2} steps every 10 s with simultaneous voltage record-
76 ing, using a potentiostat (PT2005; Kolibri.net). The fuel cell was fed by hydrogen and filtered air with gas-to-current

77 stoichiometric ratios of 1.2 and 5, respectively. Polarization curves were repeated at least 5 times, and average values
78 of peak power density and current density at a voltage of 0.6 V were used in the work. Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was
79 measured using H₂/N₂ feed with a flow rate of 40 sccm. The anode electrode, owing to its small overpotential, was
80 used as the counter and reference electrode, due to its low overpotential, while the cathode was configured as a work-
81 ing electrode. Voltammograms were recorded at dV/dt rates of 100, 50, and 20 mV s⁻¹ in the potential range from 0.08
82 to 1 V; measurements were repeated 15 times at each speed. For curves recorded at 50 mV s⁻¹, a total charge of the
83 hydrogen desorption region was defined for curves recorded at 50 mV s⁻¹, where the upper limit of integration was
84 0.4 V, and linear extrapolation of the double layer region to the lower potentials was used as a baseline. Double-layer
85 capacitance was retrieved from the slope of the current at 0.45 V vs. scan rate. Data used to calculate the total charge
86 and double layer current calculation were sampled from the 3rd, 6th, 9th, and 12th scans and then averaged.

87 Potentiostatic impedance spectroscopy (PEIS) was measured in the frequency range of 100 kHz – 100 mHz with an
88 excitation voltage amplitude of 5 mV and polarization at 0.45 V. Measurements were performed using H₂/N₂ gas feed
89 with flow rates of 50/100 sccm and 100 % of relative humidity for the anode and cathode sides, respectively. Both CV
90 and PEIS were measured using the potentiostat SP-150 (BioLogic).

91

92 **3. Results and discussion**

93 Cyclic voltammetry can be used for monitoring the electrochemically active surface of platinum catalyst and total
94 electrode/electrolyte interface area, measured by integration of H_{UPD} region and double layer capacitance (C_{dl}), re-
95 spectively. During CV measurements no additional water is formed making it more straightforward to achieve equilib-
96 rium conditions.

97

98 Figure 1 shows the total H_{UPD} charge and the double-layer capacitance as a function of the catalyst loading for catalyst
99 layers with a fixed ionomer-to-carbon ratio of 0.6. As can be seen from the figure, both the H_{UPD} charge (Fig. 1a) and
100 the C_{dl} (Fig. 1b) increase linearly with catalyst loading. This result indicates that the amount of catalyst active sites, as
101 well as the electrode/electrolyte interface area, increases linearly with catalyst loading in the range of 0.2 – 1.0
102 mg_{Pt} cm⁻² with slopes (at 100%RH) of 84.7 mC mg_{Pt}⁻¹. This, however, is not the case for catalyst particles with low Pt

103 concentration (Pt20%@Vulcan), where linearity can be broken at concentrations above 0.17 mg_{Pt} cm⁻² due to a thicker
104 catalyst layer [28]. Linear dependency for H_{UPD} charge and C_{dl} is observed in the relative humidity range from 100%
105 to 25%. However, the values of H_{UPD} charge (unlike C_{dl}) decrease with humidity for all catalyst loadings in the men-
106 tioned range of humidities. Compared to H_{UPD} values at 100 RH%, values at 25 RH% decreased by 30-50% depend-
107 ing on the catalyst loading. The decrease of H_{UPD} charge at low humidity correlates with recent findings[29], and
108 could be a result of the ionomer shrinkage [30] as well as of less developed water channels, which, according to
109 the recent MD study [31], play a significant role in proton transport. Values of C_{dl} have, however, lesser depend-
110 ency on humidity, which was also observed in [32]. Although reduced hydration of the catalyst layer could affect
111 double-layer capacitance in a similar way as H_{UPD} charge, the higher sensitivity of the latter may indicate more
112 complicated effects of humidity on hydrogen adsorption.

113 The effect of relative humidity can be further discussed in terms of the dependence of ionomer water content and
114 electrochemical active surface area (ECSA) at different platinum loadings. An equilibrium water content, which
115 is calculated from the relative humidity values (see eq. S2), in the ionomer has a dramatic effect on the ECSA
116 values, as was previously observed in [32,33]. This effect is more pronounced in catalyst layers with lower ion-
117 omer content (5-30%wt.) and almost vanishes at high content (50%wt.) [32]. The empirical relationship between
118 water content and ECSA can be written in the following form [33]:

119
$$ECSA(\lambda) = ECSA_0(1 - e^{-a\lambda}) \quad (1),$$

120 where ECSA₀ is the ECSA value at 100%RH, a – constant, λ – equilibrium water content.

121 Fitting of the experimental data by Eq. 1 (Fig.2a) shows similar behavior for all studied catalyst loadings. The
122 exponent factor, *a*, is in the range from 0.32 to 0.44, which is similar to the value of 0.32 (at 30 wt%) in [33].
123 However, contrary to the study [33], where the parameter *a* had a positive correlation with Pt loading, in a wider range
124 of loadings, we found its value fluctuating. It is worth noting that the correlation may be hidden by measurement
125 error, and a more delicate experiment is required.

126 The temperature dependency of ECSA has been previously observed in a number of publications [34-36]. The
127 decrease in the apparent value of ECSA can be explained by an increased rate of hydrogen desorption; thus, the max-
128 imum value of the hydrogen monolayer coverage at room temperature decreases from 0.77 to lower values [37].

129 Overall, an Arrhenius-type equation can be employed to describe such changes [33]:

$$130 \quad ECSA(T) = ECSA_{0,ref} \left(e^{\frac{E_A}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_{ref}} \right)} \right) \quad (2),$$

131 where $ECSA_{0,ref}$ is the ECSA value at T_{ref} – reference temperature (298K for fitting purposes), E_A is an activa-
132 tion energy term, $R = 8.31 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ is the gas constant.

133

134 As can be seen in Figure 2b, the experimental data can be fitted well using Eq. 2. at different humidities. The analysis
135 of the data only includes measurements at 100 and 75%RH due to experimental limitations in setting low levels of
136 both humidity and temperature. The fitting parameter, E_A , which combines information on H-Pt adsorption energy and
137 H-H repulsion, gets values of 2.77 and 3.67 kJ mol^{-1} for I/C ratios of 0.8 and 0.6, respectively. These values are lower
138 than those calculated in [33], which may be related to the different types of supports used in studies. It should be not-
139 ed that supported catalysts show deviations from thermodynamically predicted temperature dependencies [34] (see
140 also Fig. S1, eq. S3).

141 However, the overall effect of variation of humidity and temperature on the catalyst activity and, hence, fuel cell per-
142 formance is different. While lowering the humidity level could imply a real decrease in the number of catalyst active
143 sites (as indicated by the ECSA drop) and ultimately fuel cell performance, temperature variations, on the other hand,
144 could alter apparent values of ECSA only, rendering the temperature dependency of this parameter inadequate for per-
145 formance estimation.

146 Increasing catalyst loading and, therefore, CL thickness prolongs proton pathways to the membrane. To assess the
147 influence of loading on the proton conductivity in CL impedance spectroscopy was employed.

148

149 As can be seen from the Nyquist plot (Fig. 3), all studied MEAs have the same high-frequency resistance (HFR),
150 which corresponds to the resistance of the membrane. The same HFR for different catalyst loading, which also in-
151 cludes the contact resistance between the membrane and CL, indicates the absence of CL delamination at higher load-
152 ing as well as the similarity of testing conditions. The impedance characteristics of a fuel cell measured with N_2 sup-

153 ply at the cathode typically have linear regions, and the real part of resistance at the transition between two regions
154 can be used for the calculation of CL proton resistance [38]. The calculated proton resistance is shown in the inset of
155 Figure 3 and appears to be a linear function of catalyst loading. The linear dependency of proton resistance in the cata-
156 lyst layer on loading may indicate the fractal dimension of the proton-conducting network close to 1. This allows us to
157 conclude that the proton-conducting channels in the catalyst layer are rather straight.

158 The overall performance depends on the efficiency of the proton, electron, and mass transport as well as on several
159 active sites. Despite the plethora of parameters with complicated interdependencies defining final performance, it can
160 be easily characterised by measuring polarisation curves. Typically, the maximum power density is used for quick
161 performance assessment, while performance characterization at 0.6 V is more practical.

162

163 Figure 4 maps the performance of fuel cells with different catalyst loading operating at different humidities (detailed
164 polarization and power density curves presented in Figure S2). As can be seen from the figure, the performance of fuel
165 cells, irrespective of the catalyst loading, strongly depends on the operating humidity. Thus, all the studied systems
166 demonstrated a decline in performance when working at lower humidities. Such a result is expected due to the fact of
167 progressive ionomer dehydration in the drier environment. The proton conductivity of the ionomer decreases with the
168 degree of hydration, leading to an increase in ohmic losses. However, the performance of the fuel cell at 100%RH
169 does not reach peak values (shown by “stars” in Fig. 4). Instead, peak power density can be reached at relative humid-
170 ities between 75 and 50% for all catalyst loadings. Moreover, with an increase in catalyst loading, the peak perfor-
171 mance gravitates to lower relative humidity values. Assuming that the thickness of the catalyst layer is proportional to
172 the catalyst loading, such behavior may be related to water management effects. In this regard, at reduced humidity,
173 when saturation by water vapors is low, the formation of condensed water droplets is less favorable. This, in turn, im-
174 proves gas diffusion in the tortuous CL pores, while the condensed water droplets may reduce or block gas transport.
175 At lower humidities (25% and 0%RH), however, a drop of proton conductivity upon ionomer dehydration overrides a
176 benign effect of water droplets evaporation on the fuel cell performance. As a result, MEAs with all catalyst loadings
177 demonstrate a reduced performance.

178 An increase in catalyst loading leads to several counteracting phenomena. On the one hand, a linear increase in the

179 number of catalyst sites with loading (as shown in Fig. 1a) facilitates ORR reaction kinetics and so the total perfor-
180 mance. On the other hand, proton transfer resistance also increases with loading, which could deteriorate the perfor-
181 mance. Moreover, efficient mass transport at higher loadings is hindered, leading to performance limitations [39,40].
182 Therefore, the best performance can be reached in MEA with an optimal concentration of catalyst. Examination of
183 Figure 4 reveals that MEA with a loading of $0.4 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ has the best performance, indicating that trade-offs between
184 many parameters are established. This corresponds to the optimal value of $0.5 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ [41] demonstrated in the lit-
185 erature. To show a more detailed picture of environmental effects on fuel cell performance, the peak power density
186 was measured at different working temperatures and relative humidities.

187

188 As can be seen from Figure 5, fuel cell performance is sensitive to both temperature and humidity (detailed polariza-
189 tion and power density curves presented in Figures S3 and S4). Looking at the data measured under fully hydrated
190 conditions (100 %RH), it can be concluded that increasing temperature has a positive effect on fuel cell performance
191 as the peak power density increases from 0.79 to 0.92 W cm^{-2} as the temperature increases from 40 to $70 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. This re-
192 sult is not surprising as the increase in temperature facilitates better proton mobility and higher catalyst activity.
193 Moreover, the improved gas permeability of thin ionomer films covering catalyst particles and better gas diffusion in
194 nanosized pores also contribute to better performance [39,40]. However, when the relative humidity decreases, water
195 retention in the catalyst layer becomes more difficult; thus, proton transport drops dramatically. Therefore, peak per-
196 formance at lower relative humidities tends to shift to lower temperatures where retention of water is easier and con-
197 ductivity of protons can be maintained at sufficient levels.

198 This behavior, however, changes dramatically when the catalyst layer has higher ionomer content. Increasing the ion-
199 omer-to-carbon (I/C) ratio to 0.8 results in worse fuel cell performance as compared to that of an I/C ratio of 0.6 . Such
200 performance deterioration can be explained by mass transport problems in the catalyst layer as ionomer forms thicker
201 films over catalyst particles and blocks pores [42]. However, MEAs with an I/C ratio of 0.8 show lesser variation of
202 performance with humidity at a given temperature. Some slight improvement at intermediate humidities (25 - $50 \text{ } \%$ RH)
203 may also be related to the removal of water excess and CL pores de-blockage [43].

204 It can be concluded that samples with higher ionomer content better retain water and support a reasonable level of

205 proton conductivity, influencing overall fuel cell performance. Water retention can be extremely important when a fuel
206 cell operates at low humidity. This helps not only to improve fuel cell performance but also to prevent its deterioration
207 in the long run. It is important to note that an improvement of water retention is, however, counterintuitive, provided
208 hydrophobicity increases at the ionomer loadings of around 30 wt% [44].

209 Operation of the fuel cell at low humidity may result in the degradation of the ionomer part. As was shown previously,
210 operation at low humidity provokes the formation of hydrogen peroxide, which provokes ionomer decomposition
211 [45]. Therefore, it is practically important to study ways of mitigating the performance degradation for fuel cells
212 working in low-humidity environments. To prevent dehydration in the catalyst layer addition of ionomer may be a
213 sound strategy due to the hydrophilic treatment of the catalyst layer.

214 Fuel cells with catalyst layers with I/C ratios of 0.6 and 0.8 were tested at constant load in the potentiostatic mode.
215 Starting operation with fully hydrated MEA, the fuel cell was fed with totally dry gasses for 20 hours. Therefore, the
216 fuel cell was operating most of the time in the self-humidification regime. Although the hydration of ionomer will
217 depend on the produced current [46], we have chosen voltage control mode to approach realistic conditions. Such
218 measurements were repeated three times, and the current density was recorded as a function of time and presented in
219 Figure 6. As can be seen in the figure, at the beginning of every 20-hour cycle, fuel cell performance is higher. This
220 higher performance is observed for both I/C ratios and is related to higher hydration of the ionomer and corresponding
221 lesser proton resistance. As a fuel cell operates with dry gases, its performance gradually decreases. Interestingly, sys-
222 tems with lower ionomer content (I/C=0.6) show a continuous decrease of current density, whereas ones with an I/C
223 ratio of 0.8 after 5 hours of operation reach a stable operation. Moreover, apparent degradation can be observed for
224 systems with I/C=0.6 as every new cycle started and finished at smaller currents than the previous. This contrasts with
225 a system with I/C=0.8, where performance during three cycles shows small variation. To understand the reason for the
226 performance variation after every cycle, we measured the ECSA of fully hydrated samples, which corresponds to the
227 number of active sites.

228 Figure 7 shows the changes in ECSA as the test in a dry environment progresses. The initial ECSA of the system. As
229 can be seen from the figure, in both cases, ECSA values decrease over time. We assume that the decrease in the appar-
230 ent ECSA values is not attributed to the catalyst degradation [38], but rather to the destruction of ionomer channels
231 due to dry operation. In other words, more catalyst particles failed to fulfil the conditions of the triple phase boundary

232 [48,49]. It is remarkable that ionomer loading influences the rate of the ECSA degradation process. Catalyst layer with
233 higher ionomer content ($I/C=0.8$) demonstrates (at least in the time frame of the experiment) more than twice the low-
234 er rate of decrease of ECSA (Fig. 7). There could be several reasons explaining such observation. Firstly, the catalyst
235 layer with higher ionomer content is assumed to have better water retention. Therefore, the local hydration of ionomer
236 can be higher, and its degradation is less. Secondly, a higher thickness of the ionomer layer adds more robustness to
237 the catalyst layer even in the case of ionomer degradation. It turns out that an increase of ionomer content in the cata-
238 lyst layer is a sound strategy for optimisation for dry operation of the fuel cell catalyst layer.

239 **Conclusions**

240 In this paper, the performance of catalyst layers with Pt loadings in the range from 0.2 to 1 mg cm⁻² and ionomer car-
241 bon ratios of 0.6 and 0.8 has been investigated under different working conditions. It was found that an increase in
242 catalyst loading leads to a proportional increase in the number of active sites and proton transport resistance. Optimal
243 fuel cell performance was achieved at a loading of 0.4 mgPt cm⁻² and a relative humidity of 75%. Fuel cell perfor-
244 mance was mapped as a function of temperature and relative humidity. For a widely accepted optimal ionomer-to-
245 carbon (I/C) ratio of 0.6, at relative humidities >50, % increase of temperature in the range from 40 to 70 °C improves
246 the fuel cell performance, while at humidities <50% better performance is observed at lower temperatures. Increase of
247 the I/C ratio to 0.8 improves performance with temperature at constant humidity. Moreover, increasing of I/C ratio
248 improves the performance and durability of fuel cell at low humidity operation. These findings provide valuable in-
249 sights for optimizing catalyst layers and operating conditions in fuel cell systems.

250 **Acknowledgements**

251 The work was financially supported the Czech Science Foundation, project No. 22-03643S, structural fund project
252 PaC-NG No. CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/16_025/0007414 and "The Energy Conversion and Storage", funded as project No.
253 CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research.

254 **Reference**

255 [1] M.A. Abdelkareem, K. Elsaid, T. Wilberforce, M. Kamil, E.T. Sayed, A. Olabi, Environmental aspects of fuel
256 cells: A review, Science of The Total Environment. 752 (2021) 141803.

- 257 [2] L. Jin, X.-J. Wang, J.-W. Zhu, C.-F. Wang, T.-T. Zhou, X.-W. Zhang, Sensitivity analysis of proton exchange
258 membrane fuel cell performance to operating parameters and its applicability assessment under different conditions,
259 Energy Conversion and Management. 228 (2021) 113727.
- 260 [3] M. Hu, R. Zhao, R. Pan, G. Cao, Disclosure of the internal transport phenomena in an air-cooled proton ex-
261 change membrane fuel cell— part II: Parameter sensitivity analysis, International Journal of Hydrogen Energy. 46
262 (2021) 18589–18603.
- 263 [4] Q. Yan, H. Toghiani, H. Causey, Steady state and dynamic performance of proton exchange membrane fuel
264 cells (PEMFCs) under various operating conditions and load changes, Journal of Power Sources. 161 (2006) 492–502.
- 265 [5] W. Schmittinger, A. Vahidi, A review of the main parameters influencing long-term performance and durabil-
266 ity of PEM fuel cells, Journal of Power Sources. 180 (2008) 1–14.
- 267 [6] L. Fan, G. Zhang, K. Jiao, Characteristics of PEMFC operating at high current density with low external hu-
268 midification, Energy Conversion and Management. 150 (2017) 763–774.
- 269 [7] J.C. Kurnia, B.A. Chaedir, A.P. Sasmito, T. Shamim, Progress on open cathode proton exchange membrane
270 fuel cell: Performance, designs, challenges and future directions, Applied Energy. 283 (2021) 116359.
- 271 [8] C.Y. Ling, H. Cao, Y. Chen, M. Han, E. Birgersson, Compact open cathode feed system for PEMFCs, Applied
272 Energy. 164 (2016) 670–675.
- 273 [9] S. Jang, Y.S. Kang, J. Choi, J.H. Yeon, C. Seol, L.V. Nam, M. Choi, S.M. Kim, S.J. Yoo, Prism patterned
274 TiO₂ layers/Nafion® composite membrane for elevated temperature/low relative humidity fuel cell operation, Journal
275 of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry. 90 (2020) 327–332.
- 276 [10] Y.F. Huang, A.M. Kannan, C.S. Chang, C.W. Lin, Development of gas diffusion electrodes for low relative
277 humidity proton exchange membrane fuel cells, International Journal of Hydrogen Energy. 36 (2011) 2213–2220.
- 278
- 279 [11] Y. So, O. Kwon, S. Jeong, J. Kim, J. Moon, J. Park, H. Jang, G. Park, B. Yoo, Y. Jeong, T. Park, Enhanced water
280 retention in carbon nanotube sheets-sandwiched gas diffusion layer in polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cells oper-

281 ated under low humidity conditions, *Journal of Power Sources*. 584 (2023),233609.

282 [12] Y. Wang, W. Zhang, H. Liu, Q. Xu, L. Khotseng, Y. Cheng, H. Su, Cultivating titanium dioxide nanoarrays on gas
283 diffusion layer for advancing self-humidifying proton exchange membrane fuel cell, *Fuel*. 366 (2024), 131322.

284 [13] S. Hou, H. Wang, J. Ren, C. Yao, L. Shi, S. Liao, Enhanced low-humidity performance of proton-exchange
285 membrane fuel cell by introducing hydrophilic CNTs in membrane electrode assembly, *Progress in Natural Science:
286 Materials International*. 32 (2022) 150–156.

287 [14] M.J. Leeuwner, A. Patra, D.P. Wilkinson, E.L. Gyenge, Graphene and reduced graphene oxide based mi-
288 croporous layers for high-performance proton-exchange membrane fuel cells under varied humidity operation, *Journal
289 of Power Sources*. 423 (2019) 192–202.

290 [15] C.-W. Roh, J. Choi, H. Lee, Hydrophilic-hydrophobic dual catalyst layers for proton exchange membrane fuel
291 cells under low humidity, *Electrochemistry Communications*. 97 (2018) 105–109.

292 [16] M.K. Cho, H.-Y. Park, S.Y. Lee, B.-S. Lee, H.-J. Kim, D. Henkensmeier, S.J. Yoo, J.Y. Kim, J. Han, H.S.
293 Park, Y.-E. Sung, J.H. Jang, Effect of Catalyst Layer Ionomer Content on Performance of Intermediate Temperature
294 Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells (IT-PEMFCs) under Reduced Humidity Conditions, *Electrochimica Acta*. 224
295 (2017) 228–234.

296 [17] S. Hou, S. Liao, Z. Xiong, H. Zou, D. Dang, R. Zheng, T. Shu, Z. Liang, X. Li, Y. Li, Improvement of proton
297 exchange membrane fuel cell performance in low-humidity conditions by adding hygroscopic agarose powder to the
298 catalyst layer, *Journal of Power Sources*. 273 (2015) 168–173.

299 [18] S. Mateo, F.J. Fernandez-Morales, P. Cañizares, M.A. Rodrigo, Influence of the Cathode Platinum Loading
300 and of the Implementation of Membranes on the Performance of Air-Breathing Microbial Fuel Cells, *Electrocatalysis*.
301 8 (2017) 442–449.

302 [19] W. Liu, L. Wan, J. Liu, M. Zhao, Z. Zou, Performance improvement of the open-cathode proton exchange
303 membrane fuel cell by optimizing membrane electrode assemblies, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*. 40
304 (2015) 7159–7167.

305 [20] Y.-C. Park, H. Tokiwa, K. Kakinuma, M. Watanabe, M. Uchida, Effects of carbon supports on Pt distribution,

306 ionomer coverage and cathode performance for polymer electrolyte fuel cells, *Journal of Power Sources*. 315 (2016)
307 179–191.

308 [21] F. Vandenberghe, F. Micoud, P. Schott, A. Morin, C. Lafforgue, M. Chatenet, Low-loaded catalyst layers for
309 proton exchange membrane fuel cell dynamic operation part 1: Experimental study, *Electrochimica Acta*. 511 (2025),
310 145364.

311 [22] M. Lin, C. Hao, B. Yang, J. Liu, C. Tan, Z. Wang, Y. Xie, P.K. Shen, Z.Q. Tian, Ultra-low Pt loading cathode
312 catalyst layers with hierarchically mesoporous distribution modulation for high-performance proton exchange mem-
313 brane fuel cells, *Nano Research* (2025).

314 [23] J. Zhang, K. Wan, X. Xu, Q. Xue, Z. Jin, Z. Shan, P. Ming, J. Wang, B. Li and C. Zhang, High-performance
315 of ultra-low Pt-loaded PEMFCs: carbon-encapsulated CoFe alloy supported Pt nanoparticles as high-efficiency elec-
316 trocatalysts, *J. Mater. Chem. A*. 13 (2025), 21888-21897.

317 [24] N. Ramaswamy, A. Kongkanand, J. Wortman and W. Gu, Review—Meeting Fuel Cell Catalyst Requirements
318 for Heavy-Duty Vehicle Applications, *Journal of The Electrochemical Society*. 172 (2025), 024501.

319 [25] P. Schneider, M.h Batool, A. O. Godoy, R. Singh, D. Gerteisen, J. Jankovic and N. Zamel, Impact of Platinum
320 Loading and Layer Thickness on Cathode Catalyst Degradation in PEM Fuel Cells, *Journal of The Electrochemical*
321 *Society*. 170 (2023) 024506.

322 [26] Z. Wang, F. Zhang, B. Wang, L. Fan, C. Tongsh, S. Wu, H. Ren, J. Liu, H. Deng, Q. Du, K. Jiao, Complex
323 causality behind low-Pt-loading cathode degradation in proton exchange membrane fuel cells, *Energy*. 334
324 (2025),137663.

325 [27] USFCC Single Cell Test Protocol # 05-014, (n.d.).

326 [28] J.J. Conde, M.A. Folgado, P. Ferreira-Aparicio, A.M. Chaparro, A. Chowdhury, A. Kusoglu, D. Cullen, A.Z.
327 Weber, Mass-transport properties of electrosprayed Pt/C catalyst layers for polymer-electrolyte fuel cells, *Journal of*
328 *Power Sources*. 427 (2019) 250–259.

329 [29] X. Wang, D. Li, Y.T. Pan, K. Chen, K. Burns, Y.S. Kim, G. Wu, J. Watt, J. S. Spendelow,

330 Effect of the catalyst metal content and the carbon support on proton-exchange membrane fuel cells performance and

331 durability, *Electrochimica Acta*. 512 (2025),145490.

332 [30] H. Eskandari, D.K. Paul, A.P. Young, K. Karan, Humidity-Dependent Hydration and Proton Conductivity of
333 PFSA Ionomer Thin Films at Fuel-Cell-Relevant Temperatures: Effect of Ionomer Equivalent Weight and Side-Chain
334 Characteristics, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*. 14 (2022) 50762–50772.

335 [31] L. Fan, K. Wu, C. Tongsh, M. Zhu, X. Xie, K. Jiao, Mechanism of Water Content on the Electrochemical Sur-
336 face Area of the Catalyst Layer in the Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 10 (2019) 6409–
337 6413.

338 [32] T. Soboleva, K. Malek, Z. Xie, T. Navessin, S. Holdcroft, PEMFC Catalyst Layers: The Role of Micropores
339 and Mesopores on Water Sorption and Fuel Cell Activity, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*. 3 (2011) 1827–1837.

340 [33] K. Wu, Z. Wang, G. Zhang, L. Fan, M. Zhu, X. Xie, Q. Du, B. Zu, K. Jiao, Correlating electrochemical active
341 surface area with humidity and its application in proton exchange membrane fuel cell modeling, *Energy Conversion
342 and Management*. 251 (2022) 114982.

343 [34] A.M. Chaparro, A.J. Martín, M.A. Folgado, B. Gallardo, L. Daza, Comparative analysis of the electroactive
344 area of Pt/C PEMFC electrodes in liquid and solid polymer contact by underpotential hydrogen adsorption/desorption,
345 *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*. 34 (2009) 4838–4846.

346 [35] A. Zolfaghari, M. Chayer, G. Jerkiewicz, Energetics of the Underpotential Deposition of Hydrogen on Plati-
347 num Electrodes: I. Absence of Coadsorbed Species, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 144 (1997) 3034–3041.

348 [36] A. Zolfaghari, G. Jerkiewicz, Temperature-dependent research on Pt(111) and Pt(100) electrodes in aqueous
349 H₂SO₄, *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry*. 467 (1999) 177–185.

350 [37] T. Vidaković, M. Christov, K. Sundmacher, The use of CO stripping for in situ fuel cell catalyst characteriza-
351 tion, *Electrochimica Acta*. 52 (2007) 5606–5613.

352 [38] T. Gaumont, G. Maranzana, O. Lottin, J. Dillet, S. Didierjean, J. Pauchet, L. Guétaz, Measurement of proton-
353 ic resistance of catalyst layers as a tool for degradation monitoring, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*. 42
354 (2017) 1800–1812.

- 355 [39] Y.V. Yakovlev, M.G. Rodríguez, Y.V. Lobko, M. Vorokhta, P. Kúš, I. Matolínová, V. Matolín, Characterization
356 of gas diffusion layer transport properties by limiting current approach, *Electrochimica Acta*. 404 (2022) 139755.
- 357 [40] Y.V. Yakovlev, Y.V. Lobko, M. Vorokhta, J. Nováková, M. Mazur, I. Matolínová, V. Matolín, Ionomer content
358 effect on charge and gas transport in the cathode catalyst layer of proton-exchange membrane fuel cells, *Journal of*
359 *Power Sources*. 490 (2021) 229531.
- 360 [41] V.M. Umap, R.P. Ugwekar, Performance analysis of gas diffusion electrode with varying platinum loading
361 under different oxidant condition, *Renewable Energy*. 155 (2020) 1339–1346.
- 362 [42] S. Jeon, J. Lee, G.M. Rios, H.-J. Kim, S.-Y. Lee, E. Cho, T.-H. Lim, J. Hyun Jang, Effect of ionomer content
363 and relative humidity on polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cell (PEMFC) performance of membrane-electrode as-
364 semblies (MEAs) prepared by decal transfer method, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*. 35 (2010) 9678–
365 9686.
- 366 [43] S.H. Ahn, S. Jeon, H.-Y. Park, S.-K. Kim, H.-J. Kim, E. Cho, D. Henkensmeier, S.J. Yoo, S.W. Nam, T.-H.
367 Lim, J.H. Jang, Effects of platinum loading on the performance of proton exchange membrane fuel cells with high
368 ionomer content in catalyst layers, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*. 38 (2013) 9826–9834.
- 369 [44] S.M. Andersen, L. Grahl-Madsen, Interface contribution to the electrode performance of proton exchange
370 membrane fuel cells – Impact of the ionomer, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*. 41 (2016) 1892–1901.
- 371 [45] C. Chen, T.F. Fuller, The effect of humidity on the degradation of Nafion® membrane, *Polymer Degradation*
372 *and Stability*. 94 (2009) 1436–1447.
- 373 [46] E. Janicka, M. Mielniczek, L. Gawel, K. Darowicki, P. Landowska, The impact of air humidity on the opera-
374 tion of proton exchange membrane fuel cells determined using dynamic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy,
375 *Electrochimica Acta*. 341 (2020) 136036.
- 376 [47] W. Bi, Q. Sun, Y. Deng, T.F. Fuller, The effect of humidity and oxygen partial pressure on degradation of Pt/C
377 catalyst in PEM fuel cell, *Electrochimica Acta*. 54 (2009) 1826–1833.
- 378 [48] M. Hwang, Y.A. Elabd, Impact of ionomer resistance in nanofiber-nanoparticle electrodes for ultra-low plati-

379 num fuel cells, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*. 44 (2019) 6245–6256.

380 [49] Y.V. Yakovlev, J. Nováková, P. Kúš, T.N. Dinhová, I. Matolínová, V. Matolín, Highly developed nanostructur-
381 ing of polymer-electrolyte membrane supported catalysts for hydrogen fuel cell application, *Journal of Power Sources*.
382 439 (2019) 227084.

383

Figure 1. H_{UPD} charge (a) double layer capacitance at different humidities calculated from cyclic voltammograms for various catalyst loadings measured at 70°C .

Figure 2. ECSA dependencies on ionomer equilibrium water content (a) and temperature (b).

Figure 3. Impedance spectroscopy of MEA with the cathode catalyst loading in the range from 0.2 to 1.0 $\text{mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{cm}^{-2}$ at 70 °C and 100%RH.

387

Figure 4. Peak power density (a) and current density at 0.6 V (b) as a function of catalyst loading and relative humidity at a temperature of 70 °C. The points of the maximum performance at the given catalyst loading are indicated by stars.

388

Figure 5. Peak performance of fuel cells with cathode catalyst loading of $0.4 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and I/C ratios of 0.6 and 0.8 as a function of temperature and humidity.

389

Figure 6. Fuel cell performance was measured at $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 0 \%RH , constant voltage of 0.6 V for samples with I/C ratios of 0.6 and 0.8.

390

391

Figure 7. ECSA values measured for systems with I/C ratios of 0.6 and 0.8 during dry test protocol at 70 °C and 100%RH.

392